

THE SOUTH POLE-AITKEN BASIN AND ADJACENT REGIONS: A NEW GEOLOGICAL MAP. H. Hiesinger¹, W. Iqbal¹, L. Wueller¹, C. M. Poehler¹, C. H. van der Bogert¹, M. A. Ivanov², J. Wright³, J. W. Head⁴, A. Oetting⁵ and, B. L. Jolliff⁶; ¹Universität Münster, Germany; ²Vernadsky Inst., RAS, Russia; ³University of Leicester, UK; ⁴Brown University, USA; ⁵ESTEC, ESA, The Netherlands; ⁶Washington University in St. Louis, USA; hiesinger@uni-muenster.de.

Introduction: Located between the lunar south pole and Aitken crater, the South Pole-Aitken (SPA) basin is one of the oldest, largest, and deepest impact basins on the Moon. With its rim crossing the potentially volatile-rich south polar region, it is not only important to understand the local and regional geology of the basin itself but also the polar areas. In particular, numerous reports identified these two regions as high priority targets for scientific exploration [e.g., 1-4]. From previous work it is known that the basin likely excavated at least lower crustal and potentially also upper mantle material [5-7]. Within the SPA basin a variety of geological units were identified and mapped. These include, for example, excavated substrates (materials older than the SPA basin) [5-8], ancient basins and craters from different periods, impact melts, basalts, plains, and swirls [1-10]. Hence, the basin geology is highly complex and it is necessary to understand it as well as possible due to the implications for lunar history and evolution. In addition, because of the volatiles stored in permanently shaded regions (PSRs) on crater floors, the south polar regions is also of great interest for human and robotic exploration. To maximize the scientific return of such missions, understanding the geological context of a given landing site is paramount. Such context and perspective are usually given in geologic maps that show the temporal and spatial distribution of geological units and targets [11]. Although several maps of regions within the SPA basin have been produced recently [e.g., 12,13], a geological map of the entire SPA basin and the south polar region at a digitization scale of 1:500,000 (print scale: 1:2,000,000) was missing. Hence, we produced such a map, using modern imaging data and other sources of information and applying consistent mapping standards across the map area. We submitted this map for publication in the journal *Icarus* (Fig. 1).

Methods: Mapping was performed on Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter (LRO) Wide-Angle Camera (WAC) [14] and the Kaguya terrain camera [15] images acquired at different observation and illumination geometries. We used a geographic information system and USGS and PLANMAP standards for our geomorphological mapping [16,17]. Spectral differences were mapped in Clementine [18] and Kaguya MI [19] data, whereas topographic features were mapped using Lunar Orbiter Laser Altimeter (LOLA) digital elevation models (DEMs) and the merged LOLA/Kaguya DEM with a resolution of 59m/pixel [20]. As the southernmost latitudes of our map area suffer from very challenging illumination

geometries, i.e., low lighting casting long shadows, we used hillshade maps with various illumination conditions as a basis for mapping.

Geology: In our high-resolution mapping effort, we identified several classes of geologic features in our mapping area (Fig. 1).

Basin materials comprise the oldest geologic units within the map area. Among those, materials of the SPA basin are the oldest and hence represent an important stratigraphic marker. Similarly, materials from the Ingenii, Apollo, Schrödinger, and Orientale basins are stratigraphic markers for defining stratigraphic relationships and relative ages.

Craters materials: In our map, we classified craters <300 km by the degradation state of their rims, the distribution of their ejecta material, and their stratigraphic position with respect to adjacent geologic units. To decipher the stratigraphic age of these craters we applied the criteria established by [21].

Plains units are smooth, terrain-filling materials, which commonly occur in low-topography regions. In our geologic map, we subdivided the plains units on the basis of albedo and surface roughness (Fig. 1). We identified three types of plains: (1) relatively rough, (2) light-colored, and (3) dark-colored. On the basis of our stratigraphic investigations, we found that the rough plains are older plains and occur preferentially in topographically low regions. In general, this plains unit is characterized by a low albedo and slightly rugged texture. In contrast, light plains units exhibit a smooth surfaces and high albedo and are often observed in low-relief regions, where they occupy the floors of craters and basins. Finally, dark plains have a low albedo and smooth topography. In the map region, they are exposed on crater floors and in the central area of the SPA basin. We interpret the dark plains as products of volcanic activity, i.e., as mare basalt deposits. Support for a volcanic origin comes from our observation of various volcanic features, including domes and rills.

Context for Exploration: China was first in successfully landing within the SPA basin, i.e., in the Apollo basin and Von Karman crater. These landed missions were part of China's lunar exploration program for the SPA basin, and increased our knowledge about them dramatically [e.g., 22-24]. The Endurance mission is intended to traverse the SPA basin and to collect samples [25], while the Artemis [26] and Chang'e-7 missions will explore the South Pole. It is long known that returning samples from the SPA basin is fundamentally important to accomplish a number of scientific objectives [e.g.,

2]. For past and future sample return missions, our new map (Fig. 1) provides geological context for understanding sample origin and evolution and will aid in the selection of new landing sites. An accurate geologic map is a prerequisite for any human or robotic lander mission to ensure the selection of safe and scientifically interesting landing sites. However, our map is the global context, whereas future exploration will benefit from more detailed regional and site maps for successful missions.

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Figure 1. Geological map of the South Pole-Aitken basin and adjacent regions showing a wide variety of geologic units ranging in age from pre-Nectarian to Copernican times. The mapping scale was 1:500,000. The map is shown in a Lambert projection, centered at 157.5° S and 53° E.